

Performance Analysis of 5G and Beyond Mixed THz/FSO Relaying Communication Systems

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Abstract

This paper explores the potential of relay-assisted transmission to mitigate fading in free-space optical (FSO) systems. Our investigation focuses on assessing the performance of a dual-hop relay system for Terahertz/FSO (THz/FSO) communication. We develop an aggregated channel model incorporating various factors, including pointing errors, channel fading, and deterministic path loss. Specifically, the THz link encounters $\alpha - \mu$ fading with pointing errors, while the FSO link experiences Gamma-Gamma fading and pointing errors. We utilize amplify-and-forward relaying and derive mathematical expressions for the cumulative distribution function and probability density function of the end-to-end signal-to-noise ratio, considering the combined effects of channel fading and pointing errors. Employing the derived statistical expressions, we evaluate crucial performance metrics for the considered relaying schemes, including the average bit error rate and the outage probability. To validate our analytical findings, we conducted Monte-Carlo simulations. The results demonstrate a strong correlation between the performance of the system and the particular pointing errors and fading parameters linked to the THz/FSO connections.

Keywords: Atmospheric turbulence, dual-hop transmission schemes, free-space optical communications, gamma-gamma ($\Gamma\Gamma$) distribution, performance

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analysis, pointing errors, terahertz communications.

1. Introduction

The demand for wireless communication systems has consistently increased to meet the needs of data-intensive applications and services. One area of particular growth is the Internet-of-Things (IoT) in the beyond fifth-generation (B5G) era, where significant business requirements are expected. Consequently, it is necessary to revolutionize data transmission rates in existing wireless communication systems to address the growing need for wireless connectivity in IoT deployments. This is crucial to tackle the challenges posed by growing communication traffic [1]. Future systems such as the sixth generation (6G) and beyond are anticipated to achieve remarkable performance metrics, including peak data rates of terabits per second (Tbps) [2]. Moreover, these systems aim to support extensive connectivity density, surpassing 10 million devices per 1 km², and exhibit 100 bps/Hz spectrum efficiency. They also target experienced data rates for users ranging from 10 to 100 Gbps, 99.99999% data transmission reliability, 100-fold improvement in network energy efficiency compared to fifth-generation (5G) systems, end-to-end (e2e) latency shorter than 0.1 ms, microsecond-level jitter performance, and positioning and sensing resolution with millimeter-level accuracy [1–3].

Furthermore, the 6G wireless systems must accommodate a range of novel services, including holographic teleportation, immersive remote presence, extended reality (XR), connected robotics and autonomous systems (CRAS), and digital twins. These applications, which heavily rely on bandwidth, necessitate a 1000-fold increase in capacity compared to today's 5G cellular systems. Additionally, they require wireless functionalities that serve multiple purposes, such as communication, sensing, localization, and control. Existing wireless spectrum bands are insufficient to meet these requirements. Although millimeter-wave (mmWave) communications in the 30 - 100 GHz range have been formally integrated into 5G systems [4, 5]; mmWave systems still face challenges in sup-

porting terabits per second (Tbps) data rates and meeting the stringent quality of service criteria mentioned earlier. Given the restricted contiguous bandwidth, less than 10 GHz, available in mmWave systems under 100 GHz, achieving a spectrum efficiency of 100 bps/Hz becomes exceptionally difficult, even when employing state-of-the-art physical-layer methods [4, 6]. Consequently, there is an inevitable need to explore higher frequencies for enhanced bandwidth and spectrum utilization. Terahertz (THz) and Optical Wireless Communications (OWC), such as Visible Light Communication (VLC) and free-space optical (FSO) communications, emerge as attractive spectrum options [4, 7].

THz and OWC hold significant potential as essential technologies for effectively implementing beyond-fifth-generation (B5G) communication networks. The potential application of THz/FSO technologies is depicted in Fig. 1. These technologies offer high-speed data transmission as well as ample bandwidth, and efficiently address the existing scarcity of radio frequency (RF) communication bands [2–4, 7]. Also, the optical frequency band further supports extensive bandwidth availability and transmission rates, while also providing enhanced confidentiality and robust anti-interference capabilities [8–11]. On the other hand, the THz frequency band, characterized by its short wavelength, aligns well with the requirements of ultra-dense small-cell networks. This attribute proves advantageous for achieving extensive coverage with exceptionally fast data rates and ensuring secure transmission within B5G networks. Additionally, THz communications can function in both line-of-sight (LoS) and non-line-of-sight (NLoS) propagation scenarios and exhibit the capability to penetrate through fog and dust. [4]. However, it is important to note that THz and optical communication technologies still face various challenges, including channel fading, higher path attenuation, and antenna misalignment [1, 4].

1.1. Free-Space Optical Communication Systems

FSO systems are gaining recognition as a practical substitute for optical fiber networks, particularly in situations where optical fiber deployment is impractical or in underserved rural areas with limited broadband network connectiv-

Figure 1: Potential application of THz/FSO relaying system.

ity [12]. Depending on the deployment scenario and specific application, FSO communication systems can serve as a complement to or a substitute for RF systems. This is primarily due to their distinctive features, including high bandwidth capacity, ease of deployment, resilience against signal interference, robust transmission security, utilization of license-free spectrum, protocol transparency, support for full-duplex transmission, and infrastructure flexibility [10, 13, 14].

Furthermore, in FSO systems, Point-to-Point (PtP) or Point-to-Multi-Point (PtMP) connections are commonly utilized. To achieve high-capacity FSO connections, wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) technology can be employed. WDM enables a substantial quantity of channels per FSO connection, allowing for elastic topologies connectivity that ensures network security and overcomes geographical limitations [15–18]. This versatility renders FSO systems suitable for a range of broadband wireless applications, including enterprise connectivity, metropolitan area networks, optical fiber backup, and last-mile access networks [14, 17, 19–21].

While FSO offers notable benefits, its broad adoption has been impeded by several factors that limit its performance. One such factor is the misalignment between the transmitter and receiver in the FSO system, which results in pointing errors and additional degradation of performance [8, 10, 18, 22]. This misalignment can stem from mechanical errors in the tracking system or mechanical vibrations caused by winds or building sway. Specifically, Pointing errors manifest when the laser beam deviates in vertical (elevation) and horizontal (azimuth) directions, often modeled as independent Gaussian random variables. Also, pointing errors consist of two major components: boresight and jitter. The former pertains to the fixed displacement between the center of the laser beam footprint and the center of the detection plane, which arises due to the thermal expansion of the laser beam [10]. Additionally, the latter refers to the random offset of the beam center with reference to the detector plane, often attributed to factors such as minor seismic activity, building sway, and dynamic wind forces [10, 14, 17].

To maintain a LoS connection between the transmitter and receiver within

FSO systems, designers often need to increase the transmitter beam divergence angle. However, an excessively wide divergence angle can lead to higher laser power requirements, increasing terminal, and laser safety issues near the transmitter. Conversely, a narrow divergence angle may cause communication outages when there are building sways [23, 24]. As a result, the narrow optical beamwidths associated with FSO systems impose strict requirements for acquisition, tracking, and pointing (ATP). Therefore, it becomes crucial to have a compact and lightweight ATP system to effectively address these requirements [11, 22, 25].

In addition, the detection of the FSO link beam can be achieved using two main methods: intensity modulation/direct detection (IM/DD) and heterodyne detection. While direct detection is the dominant detection technique in OWC systems, coherent communications have been suggested as an alternative detection approach. Heterodyne detection, although more complex than IM/DD, offers advantages in mitigating thermal noise [24] and turbulence effects [20, 24, 26–28].

In addition to pointing errors, the performance of FSO links is influenced by the scintillation phenomenon, which arises from atmospheric turbulence conditions. These conditions cause fluctuations in the refractive index due to non-uniform pressure and temperature along the propagation path. Consequently, the strength of the laser beam received fluctuates, impacting the link range and system reliability [8, 10, 14, 29].

Atmospheric channel irradiance is commonly modeled using the log-normal distribution due to its ease of modeling and reliability, particularly in weak turbulence environments [26, 30]. However, researchers have explored alternative statistical models to capture the characteristics of these channels. Examples include the Lognormal-Rician [31–33], negative exponential distribution, K, I-K [34, 35], extended Generalized-K (EGK), double Weibull [36, 37], and Gamma-Gamma [26, 30] distributions. Among these, the Gamma-Gamma distribution is widely used as it encompasses all turbulence regimes, ranging from weak to strong. It serves as a comprehensive fading model for describing atmospheric

turbulence, allowing for the factorization of irradiance into two separate random processes, each following a gamma probability density function (PDF). This model effectively represents both small- and large-scale atmospheric fluctuations [12, 30, 38].

Previously, various techniques, including spatial diversity, error control coding, and cooperative diversity, have been proposed to effectively address the issues of short-range and the associated turbulence-induced fading in FSO communication networks [14, 38, 39]. Notably, among these techniques, relaying technology has garnered significant attention in the past decade. It not only enhances system capacity but also provides broader coverage with improved energy efficiency [40]. By utilizing shorter hops, relaying technology improves the performance of FSO links and extends their communication range [41, 42]. In addition to their ease of deployment and enhanced reliability, relaying systems contribute to improved connectivity and reduced transmitter power usage in wireless communication networks [40]. In this setup, one or more transitional terminals act as relays between source and destination nodes [43].

Recently, a combination of FSO and RF technologies, known as mixed RF/FSO systems, have been deployed to improve the robustness of FSO links and establish connections between access networks and backbone networks, bridging the existing connectivity gap. Consequently, there has been significant interest in studying mixed RF/FSO relaying transmission systems in academic literature [21, 44–47]. To cater to future wireless communication requirements, it becomes essential to consider THz systems in FSO communications. Therefore, there is a growing need for extensive investigation into the performance of mixed THz/FSO systems.

1.2. Terahertz Communication Systems

Over the last few decades, there has been a consistent rise in the bandwidth requirements of wireless communication systems to meet the growing demands of data-intensive applications and services. Moreover, as the capacity of wireless links in current networks nears its fundamental limit, the need to achieve higher

data rates by obtaining larger bandwidth becomes increasingly crucial. As a result, researchers have been actively investigating the potential of transitioning to higher frequency bands within the radio spectrum, such as mmWave or THz frequencies [48–50].

In 5G systems, the adoption of the mmWave band has been prominent. However, in preparation for the upcoming B5G systems, there is a growing interest in the THz frequency band, which spans from 0.1 THz to 10 THz. This attention stems from the virtually limitless bandwidth offered by THz frequencies. THz wireless transmission is projected to surpass 1 Tbps while maintaining a reasonable and feasible spectral efficiency. The introduction of THz technology is expected to revolutionize the telecommunications landscape, transforming how people communicate and access information. It brings forth notable advantages, including unlimited bandwidth, seamless data transfer, ultra-fast download speeds, and microsecond latency [1, 4, 48, 50, 51].

As aforementioned, THz waves encompass a frequency spectrum ranging from 0.1 to 10 THz, positioning them between mmWave and infrared light [1, 4, 7, 50, 52, 53]. When compared to mmWave and OWC, THz communication offers several distinct advantages. For instance, THz waves support both LoS and NLoS propagation conditions, exhibit superior directionality, possess stronger anti-interference capabilities, and provide heightened confidentiality. Additionally, THz waves can serve as a dependable alternative under adverse weather conditions like fog, rain, and dust [1, 4, 7, 48, 50, 51]. However, despite these advantages, the THz band remains underdeveloped and confronts numerous challenges across different environments. These challenges stem from inherent characteristics, such as high path loss and channel fading, as well as engineering hurdles like transceiver antenna misalignment and hardware imperfections [51, 54]. Consequently, these factors contribute to performance degradation, including system outages and limitations on propagation distance [4, 50, 51].

The attenuation of the THz signal along its path is primarily attributed to the high frequencies within this band [4, 54]. These high frequencies lead to interactions and energy absorption by molecules within the propagation medium,

rendering THz band communications more susceptible to blockages [55–57]. Consequently, significant effort has been devoted to modeling the unique characteristics of the THz channel [56, 57], assessing their impact on system performance [54, 58, 59], and proposing countermeasures [51, 56, 57, 60–62]. To counteract the effects of path attenuation, one can utilize high-gain antennas with exceptionally narrow beamwidths, thereby extending the attainable range for THz communications [54, 59].

THz-based networks exhibit reduced interference as a result of their high directional transmissions and sensitivity to blockage [54]. Conversely, the use of extremely narrow beams in THz links makes them susceptible to antenna misalignment, leading to link outages [59]. It is important to note that directional communications require precise alignment and steering of the beams to avoid the deafness problem. Therefore, the misalignment of antennas occurs because high directive antennas cannot be easily fully aligned [54, 55]. Consequently, THz-band transmissions necessitate significant overhead for beam training and alignment [55]. Lastly, the hardware imperfections associated with the RF transceiver chain in THz transmissions arise from components mismatch and manufacturing defects [54, 63].

To realize fully functional THz communication systems and harness their potential for achieving data rates in the range of several tens of Gbps, a comprehensive multidisciplinary approach is required. This approach encompasses various aspects such as reconfigurable platforms, channel characterization, adaptive transceiver designs, advanced signal processing techniques, as well as upper layer protocols that are equipped with a range of security and privacy tiers [64].

Moreover, to overcome the substantial attenuation and expand coverage in THz systems, it is necessary to employ high directivity gain antennas. However, the use of directional transmissions can only extend the link distance up to a few meters. Consequently, it is impractical to anticipate universal coverage solely through THz communications [55]. A plausible deployment scenario for future wireless systems involves the coexistence of FSO technology with THz. Therefore, by combining THz and FSO, it is possible to increase the propaga-

tion range and reduce losses owing to fading and misalignment. Additionally, as THz and FSO links operate in entirely separate frequency bands, the risk of any potential interference can be eliminated, making this combination suitable for facilitating connectivity between heterogeneous networks. Furthermore, the mixed THz/FSO system can extend range during ultra-high data rate transmissions [62].

1.3. Prior Works

Significant research endeavors have been dedicated to the analysis and assessment of performance in both THz [51, 57–59, 65–68] and FSO wireless systems [18, 22, 24, 29, 32, 33, 44, 51, 69–73]. Notably, in order to address the issue of high path loss, appropriate path-loss models were introduced for THz propagation [65, 66]. Also, in [57], a novel propagation model specifically designed for the THz band was presented, while [67] introduced a simplified molecular absorption loss model for the frequency range of 275-400 GHz. Subsequently, the performance of the THz system was investigated in [66] using the model proposed in [67]. However, these contributions have a drawback in that they overestimated the performance of the THz system by neglecting the influence of fading, which can result from aerosol scattering [58]. In contrast, [68] employed a stochastic approach to model fading as a random process. Specifically, the THz channel was characterized by an $\alpha - \mu$ fading distribution, which effectively accounted for multipath effects [54]. The $\alpha - \mu$ distribution is a versatile model that includes several significant distributions, including Gamma, Weibull, Nakagami-m, and Rayleigh, as special cases. Additionally, [68] provided experimental evidence to support the presence of shadowing in the 300 GHz frequency range.

Regarding the issue of pointing errors, several models have been proposed in the literature. The Rayleigh distribution was initially employed to model pointing error in [69], followed by the adoption of the Hoyt distribution in [74], the Rician distribution in [3], and the more general Beckmann distribution in [75]. Also, numerous studies have focused on examining the effect of pointing errors

in THz-based networks [51, 54, 59]. For instance, in [59], the consequences of antenna misalignment were examined, whereas in [51, 54, 58], the joint influence of antenna misalignment and fading in THz wireless systems was assessed with a focus on the outage probability (OP) [51, 58], error rate [51, 58], and capacity [51, 54]. Furthermore, hardware impairments arising from amplifier nonlinearities, phase noise, as well as in-phase and quadrature imbalance, were summarized in [52, 63].

The impact of pointing errors on FSO links has been extensively investigated in [18, 22, 24, 29, 32, 33, 44, 51, 69, 70]. Also, with the swift advancement of the relaying scheme, the concept of mixed RF/FSO systems has emerged as a solution to bridge the connectivity gap between backbone networks and last-mile access networks. These mixed systems aim to combine multiple RF links to support a high-rate FSO link, thereby maximizing the overall capacity and achieving significant performance enhancements [20, 38, 47]. Consequently, extensive research attention has been devoted to investigating the e2e performance of dual-hop FSO/RF systems using amplify-and-forward (AF) or decode-and-forward (DF) relaying schemes, considering both heterodyne detection and IM/DD [40, 45, 76, 77]. In the context of aperture misalignment, references [21, 45] specifically examined the OP and bit error rate (BER) performance of a dual-hop AF relaying scheme consisting of a mixed RF/FSO link. These studies assumed that the FSO and RF links experienced Gamma-Gamma and Rayleigh fading channels, respectively.

Furthermore, previous studies have conducted performance analyses of mixed FSO/RF systems, considering Nakagami- m and Gamma-Gamma fading channels [38, 40, 47], as well as Exponentiated Weibull fading channels [76]. Additionally, the performance of mixed FSO/RF systems over double generalized Gamma and extended generalized- K fading models was investigated in [77]. However, these investigations did not incorporate THz technology, which is crucial for future wireless communications. In more recent research, the performance of mixed THz/FSO systems has been explored [61, 62]. These studies presented analytical expressions for the OP [61, 62], average BER [61, 62], and

average channel capacity [61] in the context of a mixed dual-hop THz/FSO system.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, despite their significant importance, the performance of mixed THz/FSO systems has not received thorough investigation. This serves as motivation for our analysis of the mixed THz/FSO system. Specifically, we introduce a theoretical framework for quantifying its outage and error performance. Delving deeper, we consider a comprehensive system model that accounts for the key design parameters and incorporates the specific characteristics of both the THz and FSO channels.

1.4. Organization

The structure of this paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 delves into the THz/FSO relay system and channel models. Section 3 presents the PDF and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the e2e signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for the relaying system under examination. Section 4 focuses on the system's performance, where we derive expressions for the OP and average BER. Section 5 provides and discusses numerical and simulation results for the proposed system. Finally, Section 6 serves as the paper's summary and conclusion.

2. System and Channel Models

Figure 2 demonstrates our investigation of a transmission system that employs dual-hop THz/FSO communication. This system involves source (S) nodes transmitting information to a destination (D) node with the assistance of a relay (R) node. The relay node is equipped with a THz receiver and an FSO transmitter aperture. The THz link between the source and relay nodes (S-R) experiences both path-loss and misalignment errors, characterized by a $\alpha-\mu$ distribution and Rayleigh fading, respectively. Additionally, the FSO link between the relay and destination nodes (R-D) is affected by atmospheric turbulence and pointing errors, characterized by Gamma-Gamma and Rayleigh fading, respectively. To mitigate the channel attenuation, we assume that all the nodes (S, R, and D) are equipped with highly directive antennas/apertures.

Figure 2: Dual-hop THz/FSO relaying wireless system.

Moreover, in this particular scenario, the communication process consists of two hops. Initially, the signal to be transmitted originates from the source (S) and is transmitted to the relay (R) through the THz link. Assuming that the information signal, denoted as $x \in \mathbb{C}$, is conveyed over a THz wireless channel, the signal received at the relay, denoted as y_r , can be mathematically given as [54, 61]

$$y_r = \sqrt{P_1}h_{SR}s + \omega_1, \quad (1)$$

The transmitted symbol is denoted as s , the transmit power at S is represented by P_1 , the THz channel coefficient is denoted as h_{SR} , and the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance N_{01} is represented by ω_1 .

Furthermore, the electrical signal transmitted from S is received and transformed into an optical signal by R. The signal is amplified using the AF protocol. Subsequently, the amplified signal is transmitted to D through the FSO link. It is also assumed that the direct link between S and D is subjected to significant fading, to the extent that it can be disregarded. Consequently, the signal received at D, denoted as y_d , is given as [61].

$$y_d = \sqrt{P_2}Gh_{RD}\eta(\sqrt{P_1}h_{SR}s + \omega_1) + \omega_2, \quad (2)$$

where h_{RD} , η , P_2 , and ω_2 denote the FSO channel coefficient, the electrical-to-optical conversion factor, the transmitting power at R, the AWGN with variance N_{02} , respectively.

The e2e instantaneous SNR at D can be deduced as [40, 78, 79]

$$\gamma = \frac{\gamma_{SR}\gamma_{RD}}{\gamma_{RD} + C} \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_{SR} = |h_{SR}|^2\bar{\gamma}_{SR}$ and $\gamma_{RD} = (\eta h_{RD})^2\bar{\gamma}_{RD}$ denote the instantaneous received SNRs for the THz and FSO links, respectively, each with their corresponding average values $\bar{\gamma}_{SR} = P_1/N_{01}$ and $\bar{\gamma}_{RD} = \eta^2 P_2/N_{02}$, respectively, and $C = P_2/(G^2 N_{01})$ is a constant determined by the AF relay gain, G .

2.1. Channel State Statistic of the First Hop: THz Link

The THz channel coefficient, h_{SR} , in eq.(1) can be analyzed as

$$h_{SR} = h_l h_p h_f, \quad (4)$$

where h_l , h_p and h_f model the path gain, the misalignment fading, and the multipath fading, respectively.

The deterministic path-gain, h_l , can be modeled as [54]

$$h_l = \frac{c\sqrt{G_{t,1}G_{r,1}}}{4\pi f_1 d_1} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\kappa_\alpha(f)d_1\right), \quad (5)$$

where f_1 is the operating frequency, c , and d_1 represent the speed of light, and the propagation distance (S-R), respectively, whereas $G_{t,1}$ and $G_{r,1}$ represent the antenna orientation dependent gains for the THz transmission and reception, respectively. Likewise, the molecular absorption coefficient, denoted as $\kappa_\alpha(f) = \kappa_\alpha(f_1, T, \psi, p)$ subjects to the values of relative humidity, ψ , temperature, T , and atmospheric pressure, p , is given by [80]

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(f_1, T, \psi, p) = & \frac{q_1 v(q_2 v + q_3)}{(q_4 v + q_5)^2 + \left(\frac{f_1}{100c} - p_1\right)^2} \\ & + \frac{q_6 v(q_7 v + q_8)}{(q_9 v + q_{10})^2 + \left(\frac{f_1}{100c} - p_2\right)^2} \\ & + c_1 f_1^3 + c_2 f_1^2 + c_3 f + c_4. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The values of parameters in (6) are given in [54, 58].

Furthermore, the THz communication channel encounters $\alpha - \mu$ fading and misalignment fading impairments. Misalignment fading results in pointing errors. The TX (S) and RX (R) beams at the transmission distance are represented as circular shapes in the positive Cartesian $x - y$ plane. Consequently, the pointing error is described as the separation between the centers of the two beams. The PDF of $|h_p|$ can be rewritten as [10, 59]

$$f_{h_p}(x) = \frac{\xi_1^2}{A_{o1}^{\xi_1^2}} x^{\xi_1^2 - 1}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq A_{o1}, \quad (7)$$

where A_{o1} represents the portion of power gathered by the receiver when there is no displacement (full-alignment) in the S-R beam and can be evaluated as $A_{o1} = |\text{erf}(u)|^2$, $\text{erf}(\cdot)$ is the error function given by $\text{erf}(x) = (2/\sqrt{\pi}) \int_0^x e^{-u^2} du$ [81, eq. (7.1.1)], $u = \sqrt{\pi}a/\sqrt{2}w_d$, a is the radius of the reception (R) antenna effective area, w_d is the transmission beam footprint radius at distance d_1 . Also, $\xi_1 = w_{eq}/2\sigma_s$ represents the ratio between the equivalent beam-width radius, w_{eq} , and the pointing error displacement standard deviation, σ_s . The equivalent beam-width, w_{eq}^2 , can be expressed as [54, 79]

$$w_{eq}^2 = w_d^2 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \text{erf}(u)}{2u \exp(-u^2)}. \quad (8)$$

The multipath fading effect can be modelled as a generalized $\alpha - \mu$ distribution. So, the PDF of $|h_f|$ can be expressed as [82]

$$f_{h_f}(x) = \frac{\alpha_1 \mu^\mu}{\hat{h}_f^{\alpha_1 \mu} \Gamma(\mu)} x^{\alpha_1 \mu - 1} \exp\left(-\mu \frac{x^{\alpha_1}}{\hat{h}_f^{\alpha_1}}\right), \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha_1 > 0$ denotes a fading parameter, μ represents the normalized variance of the fading channel envelope, $\Gamma(\cdot)$ denotes the Gamma function [83, eq. (8.310.1)], and \hat{h}_f represents the α -root mean value of the fading channel envelop.

Moreover, the channel coefficient, h_{pf} , is a random variable that accommodates the joint impact of antenna misalignment and fading. The PDF of $|h_{fp}| = |h_f||h_p|$ can be defined as [54, 58]

$$f_{|h_{fp}|}(x) = \frac{\Theta_1 x^{\xi_1^2 - 1}}{\Gamma(\mu)} \Gamma(\Theta_2, x^{\alpha_1} \Theta_3), \quad (10)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the upper incomplete gamma function [83, eq.(8.350.2)] and Θ_1, Θ_2 and Θ_3 are give respectively as

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta_1 &= \frac{\xi_1^2 A_{o1}^{-\xi_1^2} \mu^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}}}{\hat{h}_f^{\alpha_1}} \\ \Theta_2 &= \mu - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \\ \Theta_3 &= \frac{\mu A_{o1}^{-\alpha_1}}{\hat{h}_f^{\alpha_1}} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Theorem 1

Considering the THz channel with joint effects of fading and antenna misalignment, by using the chain rule and (10), the PDF of γ_{SR} can be derived as

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{\mathcal{P}_1}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}-1} \times G_{1,2}^{2,0} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2 \end{array} \right. \right] \quad (12)$$

where $G(\cdot)$ is the Meijer G-function,

$$\mathcal{P}_1 = \frac{\Theta_1}{2h_l^{\xi_1^2} \Gamma(\mu)}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_2 = \Theta_3/h_l^\alpha.$$

Proof

See Appendix A

Moreover, by following [38, Eqs. (1) and (2)], [84, Eqs. (9) and (10)], [24, Eqs. (12) and (13)], and [46, Eqs. (7) and (10)] as well as using [83, eq. (9.315)] and [83, eq. (9.301)] with some simplification, the subsequent CDF of γ_{SR} can be derived as

$$F_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{2\mathcal{P}_1}{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}} \times G_{2,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{c} 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \quad (14)$$

2.2. Channel State Statistic of the Second Hop: FSO Link

The channel state, denoted as $h_{RD} = h_l h_a h_p$, for the FSO link is a combination of deterministic and stochastic components. The deterministic component is attributed to the path loss, represented by h_l , while the stochastic part arises from random attenuation denoted as h_a , which results from atmospheric turbulence. Additionally, there is random attenuation, h_p (the PDF of $|h_p|$ is detailed in eq. 7), stemming from geometric spreading and pointing errors. The h_l and

the PDF of h_a (assuming the $\Gamma\Gamma$ model for characterizing scintillation) in the context of the FSO channel state, can be expressed respectively as [14, 24]

$$h_l(z) = \exp(-\sigma z), \quad (15)$$

$$f_{h_a}(h_a) = \frac{2(\alpha_2\beta_2)^{(\alpha_2+\beta_2)/2}}{\Gamma(\alpha_2)\Gamma(\beta_2)} \times h_a^{(\alpha_2+\beta_2/2)-1} K_{\alpha_2-\beta_2}\left(2\sqrt{\alpha_2\beta_2 h_a}\right) h_a > 0 \quad (16)$$

where σ is the attenuation coefficient, $K_\nu(\cdot)$ denotes a modified Bessel function of the second kind and order ν [83, eq. (8.432.2)], α_2 and β_2 are the effective number of small-scale and large-scale eddies of the scattering environment, respectively. The values of α_2 and β_2 for both plane wave and spherical wave are presented in [8, 10, 11, 14, 19, 24, 25]. Also, both parameters are functions of Rytov variance, σ_R^2 , which is usually employed as a metric for determining the strength of turbulence fluctuations and can be expressed as [19]

$$\sigma_R^2 = 1.23 C_n^2 k^{7/6} L^{11/6} \quad (17)$$

where L represents the distance of propagation, k is the optical wave number defined as $2\pi/\lambda$, λ is the wavelength, and C_n^2 denotes the altitude-dependent index of refraction structure parameter.

Moreover, C_n^2 is a fundamental metric used to describe fluctuations in the atmospheric refractive index. Typical values of C_n^2 for FSO links near ground level are approximately $1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{m}^{-2/3}$ during daytime and $8.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}^{-2/3}$ at night. Additionally, it spans from $10^{-13} \text{m}^{-2/3}$ for strong turbulence conditions to $10^{-17} \text{m}^{-2/3}$ for weaker conditions. It's typical average value is around $10^{-15} \text{m}^{-2/3}$ [85, 86].

Considering the PDFs in (16) and (7), the PDF of $h_{ap} = h_a h_p$ can be expressed as [14, 24]

$$f_{h_{ap}}(h_{ap}) = \int f_{h_{ap}|h_a}(h_{ap}|h_a) f_{h_a}(h_a) dh_a \quad (18)$$

where $f_{h_{ap}|h_a}(h_{ap}|h_a)$ is the conditional probability given h_a state.

By adhering to [24, 46] and employing [83, eq. (9.315)], the subsequent PDF can be defined as

$$f_{h_{ap}}(h_{ap}) = \Xi G_{1,3}^{3,0} \left[\vartheta \left| \begin{array}{c} \xi_2^2 \\ \psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3 \end{array} \right. \right], \quad (19)$$

where $\Xi = \frac{\vartheta \xi_2^2}{\Gamma(\alpha_2)\Gamma(\beta_2)}$, $\vartheta = \frac{\alpha_2 \beta_2}{A_{o2}}$, $\psi_1 = \xi_2^2 - 1$, $\psi_2 = \alpha_2 - 1$, $\psi_3 = \beta_2 - 1$, ξ_2 and A_{o2} denotes parameters associated with the pointing errors of the FSO link.

With the Gamma-Gamma fading and pointing error assumption, the composite PDF of the instantaneous received SNRs of the FSO link, γ_{RD} , is given by [79]

$$f_{\gamma_{RD}}(\gamma) = \frac{\Xi}{2\vartheta\gamma_f} G_{1,3}^{3,0} \left[\vartheta \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \begin{array}{c} \xi_2^2 + 1 \\ \xi_2^2, \alpha_2, \beta_2 \end{array} \right. \right], \quad (20)$$

As a result, the corresponding CDF of γ_{RD} can be represented as [62]

$$F_{\gamma_{RD}}(\gamma) = \frac{\Xi}{\vartheta} G_{2,4}^{3,1} \left[\vartheta \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \begin{array}{c} 1, \xi_2^2 + 1 \\ \xi_2^2, \alpha_2, \beta_2, 0 \end{array} \right. \right], \quad (21)$$

3. End-to-End SNR Statistics

In this section, we present the CDF and PDF of the e2e SNR for the fixed-gain AF relaying system under consideration.

3.1. Cumulative Distribution Function

Theorem 3

The CDF of the e2e SNR of the considered fixed-gain AF relaying system can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\gamma}(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_1 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}} G_{2,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{c} 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \\ &+ \mathcal{G}_3 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2 - 1}{2}} G_{3+2\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1} \left[\xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \left| \begin{array}{c} \vartheta^2 C \\ \bar{\gamma}_{RD}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}_1 &= \frac{2\mathcal{P}_1}{\alpha_1 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\xi_1^2/2}} \\
\mathcal{G}_2 &= \frac{\Xi \mathcal{P}_1}{\vartheta \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\xi_1^2/2}} \\
\mathcal{G}_3 &= \frac{2^{\mu_1} \mathcal{G}_2 \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{(2\pi)^{\frac{3}{2}} \alpha_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta_1 = 1, \zeta_2 = \frac{\xi_2^2+2}{2}, \zeta_3 = 1, \zeta_4 = \frac{2-\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}, \zeta_5 = \frac{2\alpha_1-\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}, \varnothing_1 = \frac{1-\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}, \varnothing_2 = \frac{2\alpha_1-\xi_1^2-1}{2\alpha_1}, \varnothing_3 = \frac{\xi_2^2}{2}, \\
\varnothing_4 = \frac{\alpha_2}{2}, \varnothing_5 = \frac{\alpha_2+1}{2}, \varnothing_6 = \frac{\beta_2}{2}, \varnothing_7 = \frac{\beta_2+1}{2}, \varnothing_8 = 0, \varnothing_9 = 0, \varnothing_{10} = \frac{\Theta_2}{2}, \varnothing_{11} = \frac{\Theta_2+1}{2} \mu_1 = \alpha_2 + \beta_2 + \Theta_2 - \frac{7}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof

See Appendix B

3.2. Probability Density Function

Theorem 4

The corresponding PDF of the e2e SNR of the considered relaying system can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
f_\gamma(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_1 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}-1} G_{3,4}^{2,2} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{c} -\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}, 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{2} \end{array} \right. \right] \\
&+ \mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_4 \gamma^{-1} G_{1+\alpha_1,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{P}_2}{2} \right)^2 \left| \begin{array}{c} \frac{\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1}, \frac{2\alpha_1-\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1} \\ \frac{\Theta_2}{2}, \frac{\Theta_2+1}{2}, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \\
&+ \mathcal{G}_3 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2-3}{2}} G_{4+2\alpha_1,10+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1,2} \left[\frac{1-\xi_1^2}{2}, \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_5 \left| \begin{array}{c} \vartheta^2 C, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \\ \varnothing_1 \dots, \varnothing_{11}, \frac{3-\xi_1^2}{2} \end{array} \right. \right] \\
&+ \mathcal{G}_3 \alpha_1 G_{3+5\alpha_1,9+4\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1,1+2\alpha_1} \left[0, \frac{1}{\alpha_1}, \frac{\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1}, \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_5 \left| \begin{array}{c} \vartheta^2 C, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \\ \varnothing_1 \dots, \varnothing_{11}, \frac{1}{\alpha_1}, 1 \end{array} \right. \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

$$\text{where } \mu_2 = \Theta_2 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{2} + \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} - \frac{3}{2} \text{ and } \mathcal{G}_4 = \alpha_1 \frac{2^{\frac{2\mu_2-1}{2}}}{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

Proof

See Appendix C

4. Performance Analysis

This section provides the formulations for the OP and average bit error rate (ABER) of the considered AF relaying system in the context of THz/FSO communication, considering the combined effects of antenna misalignment and fading.

4.1. Outage Probability

Generally, when the received instantaneous signal-to-noise ratio falls below a specific threshold value, the system experiences an outage. So, The OP is defined as the probability that the e2e instantaneous SNR falls below a certain threshold, γ_{th} . The OP of AF relaying can be expressed as [25, 79, 84]

$$P_{out} = \Pr \left[\frac{\gamma_t \gamma_f}{\gamma_f + C} < \gamma_{th} \right] = F_\gamma(\gamma_{th}). \quad (25)$$

4.2. Average Bit Error Rate

The ABER for various modulation formats can be respectively expressed in the context of the PDF and CDF of γ as [38, 84, 87]

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_b &= \frac{1}{2\Gamma(a)} \int_0^\infty \Gamma(a, b\gamma) f_\gamma(\gamma) d\gamma, \\ &= \frac{b^a}{2\Gamma(a)} \int_0^\infty \gamma^{a-1} e^{-b\gamma} F_\gamma(\gamma) d\gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where the values of parameters a and b determine various modulation schemes. For example, $\{a = \frac{1}{2}, b = 1\}$, $\{a = \frac{1}{2}, b = \frac{1}{4}\}$, and $\{a = 1, b = 1\}$ stand for binary phase shift keying (BPSK), on-off shift keying (OOK), and differential PSK (DPSK) modulation schemes, respectively.

Theorem 3

The ABER performance of the considered THz/FSO system with the joint impact of antenna misalignment and fading (i.e., the THz and FSO links expe-

rience $\alpha - \mu$ and $\Gamma\Gamma$ fading channels, respectively) can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_b = \frac{b^a}{2\Gamma(a)} & \left\{ \mathcal{G}_5 G_{4+2\alpha_1,6}^{4,2+2\alpha_1} \left[\frac{\alpha_1^{\alpha_1}}{4b^{\alpha_1}\bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \mathcal{P}_2^2 \middle| \begin{array}{l} \kappa_1, \dots, \kappa_6 \\ \varkappa_1, \dots, \varkappa_6 \end{array} \right] \right. \\ & \left. + \mathcal{G}_6 G_{3+3\alpha_1,9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1,1+\alpha_1} \left[\begin{array}{l} \xi_0, \dots, \xi_5 \\ \emptyset_1, \dots, \emptyset_{11} \end{array} \middle| \frac{\vartheta^2 C}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64} \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{b\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\alpha_1} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_5 = \mathcal{G}_1 \frac{2^{\mu_1} \alpha_1^{a'_1 - \frac{1}{2}} b^{-a'_1}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}}}$, $\mathcal{G}_6 = \mathcal{G}_3 \frac{\alpha_1^{a'_2 - \frac{1}{2}} b^{-a'_2}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{\alpha_1 - 1}{2}}}$. $a'_1 = a + \frac{\xi_1^2}{2}$, $a'_2 = a + \frac{\xi_1^2 - 1}{2}$, $\xi_0 = \frac{1 - \alpha_1}{\alpha_1}$, $\mu_1 = \frac{2\Theta_2 - 3}{2}$, $\kappa_1 = \frac{1 - a'_1}{\alpha_1}$, $\kappa_2 = \frac{\alpha_1 - a'_1}{\alpha_1}$, $\kappa_3 = \frac{\alpha_1 - \xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}$, $\kappa_4 = \frac{2\alpha_1 - \xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}$, $\kappa_5 = \frac{1}{2}$, $\kappa_6 = 1$, $\varkappa_1 = 0$, $\varkappa_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, $\varkappa_3 = \frac{\Theta_2}{2}$, $\varkappa_4 = \frac{1 + \Theta_2}{2}$, $\varkappa_5 = -\frac{\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}$, $\varkappa_6 = \frac{\alpha_1 - \xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1}$.

Proof

See Appendix D

5. Numerical Results and Discussions

This section utilizes numerical analysis to showcase the performance of the THz/FSO relay-assisted communication system and provides the numerical outcomes of the performance metric introduced in Section 4 concerning the average link SNR. In addition, we incorporate Monte Carlo simulations, averaging over 10^6 channel realizations, in conjunction with the analytical results to validate the precision of the numerical expressions.

The simulations were carried out using the MATLAB[®] software package, involving the generation of 10^6 random variables corresponding to the specific channels under examination. Furthermore, we selected a 1550 nm wavelength window for its relatively lower susceptibility to fading effects, conforming to the standard transmission window used in fiber communication systems [88–90]. Additionally, Table 1 presents a compilation of various system parameters commonly employed in practical THz and FSO communication systems [8, 14, 61, 62, 80]. It is worth noting that, unless explicitly specified, we used the values from this parameter list for our simulations. Likewise, we assumed a common threshold value of $\gamma_{th} = 5$ dB.

Moreover, to characterize the variations in irradiance, we have employed parameters $\alpha_1 = 1.2$, $\mu = 1.7$, $\xi_1 = 1.5$, and $\xi_2 = 1.2$, alongside varying values of Rytov variance denoted as σ_R^2 . In this context, we have investigated the impact of different values of σ_R^2 (specifically, $\sigma_R^2 = 0.2, 1.6, 3.5$) on the e2e OP of the THz/FSO link. These values correspond to weak, moderate, and strong

Table 1: List of system parameters

	Parameter	Symbol	Value
SRC	Relative humidity (%)	ψ	50
	Temperature (°K)	T	296°
	Atmosphere pressure (Pa)	P	101325
FSO Link	Large-scale eddy	α_2	4.22, 4.03, 11.65
	Small-scale eddy	β_2	1.36, 1.91, 10.12
	Rytov variance	σ_R^2	0.2, 1.6, 3.5
	Refractive-index ($\text{m}^{-2/3}$)	C_n^2	1.01×10^{-14} , 8.04×10^{-14} , 1.76×10^{-13}
	Pointing error parameter	ξ_2	1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.4
	Wavelength (nm)	λ	1550
	Link distance (km)	L	1
	SNR (dB)	γ	0 – 30
	Equivalent beam-width radius (cm)	w_{eq}	100
THz Link	Frequency (GHz)	f	300
	Propagation distance (m)	d_1	50
	Antenna gains (dBi)	$G_t = G_r$	55
	Fading parameter	α_1	1.1, 1.2, 2.3
	Fading parameter	μ	1.1, 1.7, 2.1
	Pointing error parameter	ξ_1	1.2, 1.5, 1.9, 2.3

Weak Turbulence $\implies \alpha_2 = 11.65, \beta_2 = 10.12, \sigma_R^2 = 0.2, C_n^2 = 1.01 \times 10^{-14} \text{m}^{-2/3}$.

Moderate Turbulence $\implies \alpha_2 = 4.03, \beta_2 = 1.91, \sigma_R^2 = 1.6, C_n^2 = 8.04 \times 10^{-14} \text{m}^{-2/3}$.

Strong Turbulence $\implies \alpha_2 = 4.22, \beta_2 = 1.36, \sigma_R^2 = 3.5, C_n^2 = 1.76 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^{-2/3}$.

SRC: Standard Reference Conditions

Figure 3: Differences in atmospheric turbulence conditions and their effect on the OP at varying average SNR levels in the THz/FSO relaying system.

turbulence conditions, as indicated in Table 1. The results illustrated in Fig. 3 validate that the proposed model aligns with the outcomes obtained from Monte-Carlo simulations. Furthermore, they indicate that an increase in the intensity of turbulence fluctuations leads to a higher OP. To put it in perspective, for an OP of 10^{-2} , $\sigma_R^2 = 0.1$ provides an improvement of approximately 8 dB compared to $\sigma_R^2 = 1.6$.

Figure 4 displays the OP of a THz/FSO relaying system across various average SNR levels, considering different fading parameter combinations. This analysis is conducted under weak turbulence conditions, defined by $\alpha_2 = 11.65$, $\beta_2 = 10.12$, $\sigma_R^2 = 0.2$, and $C_n^2 = 1.01 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$, and it explores three distinct sets of fading parameters: $\alpha_1 = 1.1$, $\mu = 1.1$; $\alpha_1 = 1.2$, $\mu = 1.7$; and $\alpha_1 = 2.3$, $\mu = 2.1$. Furthermore, the pointing error parameters, ξ_1 and ξ_2 , are held at 1.5 and 1.2, respectively. The results presented in Figure 4 reveal that higher values of α_1 and μ correspond to improved OP, as the severity of fading in the link is substantially reduced. For instance, for an OP of 10^{-2} , the fading parameters: $\alpha_1 = 1.2$, $\mu = 1.7$; and $\alpha_1 = 1.1$, $\mu = 1.1$ require about 30 dB and 40 dB, respectively.

Furthermore, we explore the influence of the ratio between the equivalent beam radius w_{eq} and the standard deviation of pointing error displacement, σ_s .

Figure 4: OP of the relaying system at different average SNR considering various fading parameter scenarios.

This analysis aims to assess the combined impacts of atmospheric turbulence and pointing errors on the system's outage performance. To this end, we consider a scenario of moderate turbulence (specifically, $\alpha_2 = 4.03, \beta_2 = 1.91, \sigma_R^2 = 1.6, C_n^2 = 8.04 \times 10^{-14} \text{m}^{-2/3}$), with fading parameters $\alpha_1 = 1.2, \mu = 1.7$, and varying values of ξ_1 (i.e., $\xi_1 = 1.2, 1.5, 1.9, 2.3$) and ξ_2 (i.e., $\xi_2 = 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.4$). The results of this investigation are depicted in Fig. 5. These findings suggest that as ξ_1 and ξ_2 decrease, their detrimental impact on the system's performance

Figure 5: Differences in pointing errors and their influence on the outage probability at varying average SNR levels in the THz/FSO relaying system.

intensifies, resulting in a significant decline in outage performance.

Additionally, we investigate the impact of varying the channel parameters α_2 within the range (4.22, 4.03, 11.65) and β_2 within the range (1.36, 1.91, 10.12) on the error probability performance of a dual-hop mixed THz/FSO wireless communication system. This analysis is conducted with $\alpha_1 = 1.2$, $\mu = 1.7$, $\xi_1 = 1.5$, $\xi_2 = 1.2$, and the assumption that the modulation-specific constant terms are $a = \frac{1}{2}$ and $b = 1$, representing a case of BPSK modulation format. The ABER plot is displayed in Fig. 6. It is evident that an increase in the values of α or β results in a reduction in the adverse impact of atmospheric turbulence. Also, we observe that the ABER increases with an increase in σ_R^2 . For instance, to attain an ABER of 10^{-2} , when $\sigma_R^2 = 0.2$, approximately 25 dB is required. This required value subsequently escalates to about 40 dB for the same ABER when $\sigma_R^2 = 3.5$. These results highlight that an increase in σ_R^2 leads to a deterioration in system performance.

Moreover, to evaluate the combined effects of atmospheric turbulence and pointing errors on the system's error probability performance, we examine a scenario involving moderate turbulence conditions (specifically, $\alpha_2 = 4.03, \beta_2 = 1.91, \sigma_R^2 = 1.6, C_n^2 = 8.04 \times 10^{-14} \text{m}^{-2/3}$). This analysis is carried out with

Figure 6: Differences in atmospheric turbulence conditions and their influence on the ABER with varying average SNR.

Figure 7: Differences in pointing errors and their influence on the ABER in the THz/FSO relaying system.

fading parameters $\alpha_1 = 1.2$ and $\mu = 1.7$. In this context, we vary the values of ξ_1 (i.e., $\xi_1 = 1.2, 1.5, 1.9, 2.3$) and ξ_2 (i.e., $\xi_2 = 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.4$). The results of this investigation are presented in Fig. 7. These findings indicate that as ξ_1 and ξ_2 decrease, their detrimental impact on the system's ABER becomes more pronounced.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we have investigated the performance of a dual-hop THz-FSO transmission scheme, using practical system parameters to estimate its performance. Our proposed hybrid system consists of two key components: the backhaul THz link and the access FSO link, both employing the amplify-and-forward protocol for relaying. We have assumed that the backhaul THz link is subject to generalized $\alpha - \mu$ fading, while the access FSO link experiences Gamma-Gamma fading. Additionally, both links are affected by pointing errors. Considering the combined impact of these pointing errors and multipath fading, we have derived analytical expressions for the probability density function and cumulative distribution function of the signal-to-noise ratio. These expressions are subsequently used to compute the outage probability for the relaying system

under investigation. Our findings underscore the significant influence of the specific pointing error and fading parameters associated with the THz-FSO links on the system's performance.

Appendix A

The PDF of the THz link' SNR

In this appendix, we derive the PDF of the SNR for the THz link, denoted as $f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma)$. Considering the THz channel with joint effects of fading and antenna misalignment, by using $\gamma_{SR} = h_l^2 |h_{fp}|^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}$, we define the PDF of γ_{SR} as

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = f_{|h_{fp}|} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}}} \right) \cdot \left| \frac{d}{d\gamma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}}} \right) \right| \quad (28)$$

Simplifying the derivative of the square root, we have

$$\frac{d}{d\gamma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}}} \right) = \frac{1}{2h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \quad (29)$$

Substituting (29) in (28), we have

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{1}{2h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}} f_{|h_{fp}|} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}}} \right) \quad (30)$$

By using (10) and (30), $f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma)$ can be expressed as

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{\Theta_1}{2h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR} \Gamma(\mu)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2} - 1} \quad (31)$$

$$\times \Gamma \left(\Theta_2, \left(\frac{\gamma}{h_l^2 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \Theta_3 \right) \quad (32)$$

This is in agreement with [91, eq. (5)] and [80, eq. (6)]. So, $f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma)$ can be defined as

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{\mathcal{P}_1}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2} - 1} \times \Gamma \left(\Theta_2, \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \right) \quad (33)$$

Also, based on (33) and by using [81, eq. 6.5.1], [92, eq. 11.1.9.2], and [93, eq. 11.5-1], we write $f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma)$ as

$$f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) = \frac{\mathcal{P}_1}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}\Gamma(\Theta_2)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}}\right)^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}-1} \times \int_{\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}}\right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2}^{\infty} t^{\Theta_2-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (34)$$

Considering the integral as the incomplete gamma function and by using transformation in [83, eq.(8.301)] and [94, Eq. (8.4.16.2)], the PDF of γ_{SR} , given in (33) can be rewritten as (12). This agrees with [95, eq. (7)] and [96, eq. (4)].

Appendix B

CDF of the End-to-End SNR

In this appendix, we derive the CDF, $F_\gamma(\gamma)$, of the e2e SNR γ .

For the AF relaying system, the CDF of the e2e SNR can be formulated as [38, 84]

$$\begin{aligned} F_\gamma(\gamma) &= \text{P} \left(\frac{\gamma_{SR}\gamma_{RD}}{\gamma_{RD} + C} < \gamma \right) \\ &= \int_0^\infty \text{P} \left[\frac{\gamma_{SR}\gamma_{RD}}{\gamma_{RD} + C} < \gamma \middle| \gamma_{RD} \right] f_{\gamma_{RD}}(\gamma) d\gamma_{RD} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

From [38, eq. (A.3)] and [84, eq. (14)], (35) can be rewritten as

$$F_\gamma(\gamma) = F_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma) + \mathcal{I}_1(\gamma) \quad (36)$$

where $\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma)$ is expressed as

$$\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma) = \int_\gamma^\infty F_{\gamma_{RD}} \left(\frac{C\gamma}{t-\gamma} \right) f_{\gamma_{SR}}(t) dt \quad (37)$$

Substituting the expressions for $f_{\gamma_{SR}}(\gamma)$ and $F_{\gamma_{RD}}(\gamma)$ in (12) and (21) respectively, into (37) with some simplification, we write $\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma)$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_2 \int_{\gamma}^{\infty} t^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}-1} \\
&\times \mathbf{G}_{2,4}^{3,1} \left[\vartheta \left(\frac{C\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{1}{(t-\gamma)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left| \begin{array}{c} 1, \xi_2^2 + 1 \\ \xi_2^2, \alpha_2, \beta_2, 0 \end{array} \right. \right] \\
&\times \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,0} \left[\frac{\mathcal{P}_2}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} t^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \left| \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2 \end{array} \right. \right] dt
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

Also, using [97, eqs. (07.34.16.0003.01) and (07.34.21.0085.01)] and [94, eq. (2.24.2.2)] after some algebraic transformations and by lowering the order using [94, eqs. (8.2.2.8) and (8.2.2.9)] and [97, eqs. (07.34.03.0001.01) and (07.34.03.0002.01)], we expressed $\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma)$ as

$$\mathcal{I}_1(\gamma) = \mathcal{G}_3 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2-1}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{3+2\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1} \left[\begin{array}{c} \xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \\ \emptyset_1, \dots, \emptyset_{11} \end{array} \left| \frac{\vartheta^2 C}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \right. \right] \tag{39}$$

Therefore, based on (14), (36), and (39), the CDF of the considered system can be defined as (22).

Appendix C

PDF of the End-to-End SNR

To evaluate the corresponding PDF, $f_{\gamma}(\gamma)$, we differentiate the CDF in (22) with respect to γ as

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{\gamma}(\gamma) &= \frac{d}{d\gamma} F_{\gamma}(\gamma) \\
&= \frac{d}{d\gamma} \left\{ \mathcal{G}_1 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{2,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{c} 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \mathcal{G}_3 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2-1}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{3+2\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1} \left[\begin{array}{c} \xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \\ \emptyset_1, \dots, \emptyset_{11} \end{array} \left| \frac{\vartheta^2 C}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \right. \right] \right\} \\
&= \frac{d}{d\gamma} \{d_1(\gamma) + d_2(\gamma)\}
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Using product rule along with [97, eq. (07.34.20.0005.01) and (07.34.20.0017.02)] and [94, eq. (8.2.2.40)], together with lowering the order of Meijer's G-function

using [94, eqs. (8.2.2.8) and (8.2.2.9)] and [97, eqs. (07.34.03.0001.01) and (07.34.03.0002.01)], we expressed $d_1(\gamma)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\gamma} \{d_1(\gamma)\} = & \mathcal{G}_1 \left\{ \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}-1} \mathbf{G}_{3,4}^{2,2} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{l} -\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}, 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{2} \end{array} \right. \right] \right. \\ & \left. + \mathcal{G}_4 \gamma^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{1+\alpha_1,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{P}_2}{2} \right)^2 \left| \begin{array}{l} \frac{\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1}, \frac{2\alpha_1-\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1} \\ \frac{\Theta_2}{2}, \frac{\Theta_2+1}{2}, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{2\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Moreover, by using [98, eq. (6)], we write $d_2(\gamma)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\gamma} \{d_2(\gamma)\} = & \mathcal{G}_3 \left\{ \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2-3}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{4+2\alpha_1,10+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1,2} \left[\begin{array}{l} \frac{1-\xi_1^2}{2}, \xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \\ \emptyset_1, \dots, \emptyset_{11}, \frac{3-\xi_1^2}{2} \end{array} \left| \frac{\vartheta^2 C}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64\bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \right. \right] \right. \\ & \left. + \alpha_1 \mathbf{G}_{3+5\alpha_1,9+4\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1,1+2\alpha_1} \left[\begin{array}{l} 0, \frac{1}{\alpha_1}, \frac{\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1}, \xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \\ \emptyset_1, \dots, \emptyset_{11}, \frac{1}{\alpha_1}, 1 \end{array} \left| \frac{\vartheta^2 C}{\bar{\gamma}_{RD}}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64\bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \right. \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Hence, by substituting (41), (42), and (40), the PDF of the considered system can be expressed as (24).

Appendix D

Average Bit Error Rate of THz/FSO Relaying Systems

Starting from (22) and (26), the ABER of the considered systems is formulated as

$$\bar{P}_b = \frac{b^a}{2\Gamma(a)} \{ \mathcal{I}_2(\gamma) + \mathcal{I}_3(\gamma) \} \quad (43)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_2(\gamma) &= \int_0^\infty \gamma^{a-1} e^{-b\gamma} \{_{,,1}\} d\gamma \\ \mathcal{I}_3(\gamma) &= \int_0^\infty \gamma^{a-1} e^{-b\gamma} \{_{,,2}\} d\gamma \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{r}_1 &= \mathcal{G}_1 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2}{2}} G_{2,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{l} 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \\ \mathfrak{r}_2 &= \mathcal{G}_3 \gamma^{\frac{\xi_1^2-1}{2}} G_{3+2\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1} \left[\xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \left| \begin{array}{l} \vartheta^2 C \\ \bar{\gamma}_{RD}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

With some algebraic simplifications and manipulations, we express $\mathcal{I}_2(\gamma)$ and $\mathcal{I}_3(\gamma)$, respectively as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_2(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_1 \int_0^\infty \gamma^{a'_1-1} e^{-b\gamma} G_{2,3}^{2,1} \left[\left(\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_2 \left| \begin{array}{l} 1 - \frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1}, 1 \\ 0, \Theta_2, -\frac{\xi_1^2}{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] d\gamma \\ \mathcal{I}_3(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_3 \int_0^\infty \gamma^{a'_2-1} e^{-b\gamma} G_{3+2\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1} \left[\xi_1, \dots, \xi_5 \left| \begin{array}{l} \vartheta^2 C \\ \bar{\gamma}_{RD}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64 \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \gamma^{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

By using [94, eq. (2.24.1.1)], [97, eq. (07.34.21.0088.01)], and [99, Section 5.6.3, eqs. (1) and (17)] with some simplifications, (46) can be represented in closed-form using the Meijer's G function as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_2(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_1 \frac{2^{\mu_1} \alpha_1^{a'_1-\frac{1}{2}} b^{-a'_1}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{\alpha_1-1}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}} G_{4+2\alpha_1, 6}^{4, 2+2\alpha_1} \left[\frac{\alpha_1^{\alpha_1}}{4b^{\alpha_1} \bar{\gamma}_{SR}^{\alpha_1}} \mathcal{P}_2^2 \left| \begin{array}{l} \kappa_1, \dots, \kappa_6 \\ \varkappa_1, \dots, \varkappa_6 \end{array} \right. \right] \\ \mathcal{I}_3(\gamma) &= \mathcal{G}_3 \frac{\alpha_1^{a'_2-\frac{1}{2}} b^{-a'_2}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{\alpha_1-1}{2}}} G_{3+3\alpha_1, 9+2\alpha_1}^{8+2\alpha_1, 1+\alpha_1} \left[\xi_0, \dots, \xi_5 \left| \begin{array}{l} \vartheta^2 C \\ \bar{\gamma}_{RD}, \frac{\mathcal{P}_2^2}{64} \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{b \bar{\gamma}_{SR}} \right)^{\alpha_1} \end{array} \right. \right] \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Therefore, based on (43) and (47), the ABER of the considered THz/FSO relaying systems can be defined as (27).

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Conflicts of Interest Statement

The authors listed below affirm that they have no affiliations, relationships, or involvements with any entity or organization that could pose a financial conflict of interest, such as receiving honoraria, educational grants, participating in speakers' bureaus, employment, holding memberships, owning stocks, engaging in consultancies, or having any other financial interest. They also confirm that they have no non-financial interests, including personal or professional relationships, knowledge, affiliations, or beliefs, that are related to the subject matter or materials presented in this manuscript.

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